

**OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING
RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGI VA SIFATIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI
OMILLAR**

**FACTORS INFLUENCING THE COMPETITIVENESS AND
QUALITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS**

**ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА
КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТЬ И КАЧЕСТВО ВЫСШИХ
УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim xizmatlarining raqobatbardoshligi va sifatiga, shuningdek bitiruvchilarning mehnat bozorida raqobatbardoshligi va oliy ta'lim xizmatlari darajasiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar va takliflar berilgan.

ANNOTATION

This article provides practical recommendations and suggestions on factors that influence the competitiveness and quality of higher education services, as well as the competitiveness of graduates in the labor market and the level of higher education services.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье даются практические рекомендации и предложения по факторам, влияющим на конкурентоспособность и качество услуг высшего образования, а также на конкурентоспособность выпускников на рынке труда и уровень услуг высшего образования.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

ta'lim xizmatlari, o'quv jarayoni, mehnat bozori, bitiruvchilarning raqobatbardoshligi, oliy ta'lim xizmatlari sifati

KEYWORDS

education services, educational process, labor market, competitiveness of graduates, quality of higher education services

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

образовательные услуги, образовательный процесс, рынок труда, конкурентоспособность выпускников, качество услуг высшего образования

INTRODUCTION

The development of education services in our country and its place in socio-economic policy, as well as its interaction with other sectors and fields, is becoming increasingly important in achieving the complex tasks of improving the activities of education services. The current education system, especially through critical analysis of higher education, is presenting various goals and perspectives based on the requirements and needs of the modern new education system. Therefore, for the comprehensive and rapid development of our republic, it is necessary to clearly define the goals of "training competitive and highly qualified specialists in foreign educational institutions, as well as improving training and skills in Uzbekistan" [1].

According to the International Labor Organization, more than 55 million young people aged 15-24 worldwide (13% of the total) are employed in low-paying jobs (earning less than \$1.9 a day) [2].

This situation has created a separate order for the preparation of competitive personnel demanded by the modern labor market. In Uzbekistan, in order to prepare graduates for the labor market, attention is paid to modernizing the higher education system by higher education institutions, which encourages the creation of highly skilled competitive personnel with creative thinking. As emphasized by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "A national qualification system is being developed to match the qualifications with the international labor market. This system provides opportunities for training personnel in more than 9,000 professions. Higher education is a wealth, an intellectual asset that enables our youth to work successfully, to

become knowledgeable and to create all conveniences for their education" [3].

MAIN PART

The level of competitiveness of graduates in the field of higher education is explained by the interaction between the education system and the labor market. In this regard, according to the opinion of the scientist U.V. Maksimov, "the competitiveness of a graduate is a set of key competencies, important and valuable directions that enable a person to successfully carry out activities in society, ensuring the general, non-transferable qualities of the individual" [4].

Therefore, in order to organize the training of graduates by higher education institutions in a systematic manner, it is necessary to pay attention to the following three main trends:

1. The increasing importance of higher education institutions in developing human capital in economic growth.
2. The increasing demand for lifelong and continuous education.
3. The intensification of competition for talented youth. In this regard, it is necessary to note that in the near future, education institutions, corporations, and even countries will compete for young talents [5].

In addition, the transformation of the content of higher education towards a new stage, which contributes to the sustainable development of social and economic sectors, plays an important role in finding its place in the labor market and producing highly qualified personnel. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the outcomes of graduates who have completed higher education programs (Table 1).

Table 1

Change in the number of specialists who have completed higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan, by regions, for the years 2016-2022, %¹

¹ It was compiled based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Areas	academic years						Growth in 2016-2022
	2016/ 2017	2017/ 2018	2018/ 2019	2019/ 2020	2020/ 2021	2021/ 2022	
Republic of Karakalpakstan	3,9	4,3	4,5	4,3	5,5	6,5	1,7
regions:							
Andijan	4,0	4,2	4,8	4,3	4,6	6,4	1,6
Bukhara	3,4	3,4	3,5	3,8	4,8	6,2	1,8
Jizzakh	2,3	2,7	2,9	2,9	3,9	3,6	1,6
Kashkadarya	3,1	3,6	3,8	3,9	5,2	5,9	1,9
Navoi	2,1	2,2	2,3	2,4	3,1	3,9	1,9
Namangan	2,7	2,9	3,0	3,2	4,1	5,5	2,0
Samarkand	6,0	6,4	6,9	6,8	7,2	8,5	1,4
Sirdaryo	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,6	2,2	2,2
Surkhandarya	1,7	1,9	2,0	2,1	3,3	3,6	2,1
Tashkent	1,8	1,7	2,7	2,8	4,1	3,7	2,1
Ferghana	4,6	4,8	4,6	4,8	5,8	9,3	2,0
Khorezm	2,0	2,2	2,2	2,4	3,2	4,2	2,1
Tashkent city	25,5	26,1	26,1	26,1	27,5	34,4	1,3
By republic	64,1	67,4	70,3	70,8	83,9	103,9	1,6

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that in our country, the number of specialists graduating from higher education institutions has been steadily increasing over the past few years, with the number of graduates reaching 64,100 in 2017 and 103,900 in 2021 in the Jizzakh region, which is the subject of research, it can be observed that this indicator has increased by 1.6%.

Based on conducted research, graduates are divided into three main groups based on their competitiveness:

The first group - professional qualifications are considered as the basis for their competitiveness, including the level of educational program, complexity, competency, and other aspects of improving knowledge and expertise (including diplomas, certificates, educational forms, and specialization diplomas).

The second group - The presence of ambitions specific to the professional characteristics and their assessment and advantages in terms of their capabilities and qualifications.

The third group - The specific point of view of each graduate on their place in the labor market and marketing capabilities, their own career plans, and their adaptability in the future employment process.

According to J.H. Bobonazarov's opinion, "Increasing the quotas for admission to educational institutions in various fields in our republic in recent years is strengthening the issue of employment of graduates with high qualifications. This situation is likely to continue in the coming years. The low level of investment attractiveness in rural areas, as a result, the underdevelopment of production and service sectors based on high technologies also undermines the competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions in the field of modern specialization and forces them to work abroad" [6].

Based on the conducted research, the need for a comprehensive assessment of the quality of higher education services and the assessment methods of competitiveness and competitiveness, as well as the necessity of a

complex assessment in this field, has been identified. In this regard, the comprehensive methodology for assessing the quality of higher

education services has been developed and proposed as a separate stage of assessment methodology, as indicated in Figure 1.

Formation of goals for evaluating the quality of higher education services	Factors influencing the improvement of the quality of higher education
	1. Identifying the mechanism for improving the competitiveness of learners
	2. Identifying factors that influence the competitiveness of education and upbringing
	3. Analyzing the quality of preparation of students based on the formation of their competitiveness during the learning process at higher education institutions
	4. Analyzing the labor market situation for finding a job, acquiring a job, and gaining competitive opportunities
	5. Analyzing potential options for employment activities and supporting graduates' employment.
	6. Modeling the system of indicators for assessing the competitiveness of the complex
	7. Developing recommendations for improving the level of competitiveness of graduates
	8. Improving the methodology for evaluating the quality of higher education services and the competitiveness assessment methodology
	9. Studying the qualitative and quantitative development of science
10. Accelerating the modernization of scientific infrastructure and expanding the scope of speeding up the process of modernizing scientific infrastructure	

1- Introduction. The quality of higher education services according to the level of complexity ²

This methodology was developed based on the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education, as well as the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approving the Concept for the development of science until 2030." The quality of higher education services is measured by how prepared a professor-teacher is for conducting classes and organizing it. On the other hand, it also reflects the pedagogical and scientific competence of professors and teachers.

CONCLUSION

In our opinion, the quality of higher education services according to the level of complexity is a mechanism for shaping students' competitiveness, analyzing the quality of student preparation, improving the competitiveness

assessment system for complex evaluation, developing recommendations for improving graduates' competitiveness, and improving the methodology for evaluating the quality of higher education services and competitiveness assessment. In addition to this, this methodology includes major steps such as analyzing the quality of student preparation for complex evaluation, analyzing labor market conditions, modeling a system of indicators for assessing competitiveness, and developing recommendations for improving the level of competitiveness of graduates. In addition to this, this methodology is distinguished by its focus on developing an uninterrupted professional education system throughout a person's life.

² Grouped by author

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